

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY TO DEVELOP PROFESSIONAL AND COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS (AS AN EXAMPLE OF TEACHING ENGLISH)

Nargiza Samandarova Muxammadovna

Tashkent State University of Economics

ABSTRACT

Training of future economists is a direction that requires a specific methodology. First of all, it is necessary to develop professional competences in the representatives of this field, as well as communicative competences are an integral part of the field. This scientific research is devoted to the discussion of the necessity, methodology and importance of developing professional and communicative competences in the process of training future economists.

Keywords: *teacher, communication skills, professional competencies, economist, integrated learning, communicative culture, method.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ БУДУЩИХ ЭКОНОМИСТОВ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Подготовка будущих экономистов – направление, требующее определенной методики. В первую очередь необходимо развивать профессиональные компетенции у представителей данной сферы, так как коммуникативные компетенции являются неотъемлемой частью сферы. Данное научное исследование посвящено обсуждению необходимости, методологии и значения развития профессиональных и коммуникативных компетенций в процессе подготовки будущих экономистов.

Ключевые слова: *преподаватель, коммуникативные способности, профессиональные компетенции, экономист, интегрированное обучение, коммуникативная культура, метод.*

BO‘LAJAK IQTISODCHILARNING KASBIY VA KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI (INGLIZ TILI O‘QITISH MISOLIDA)

ANNOTATSIYA

Bo‘lajak iqtisodchilarni tayyorlash o‘ziga xos metodologiyani talab etuvchi yo‘nalish hisoblanadi. Ushbu soha vakillarida avvalo kasbiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish lozim, shuningdek kommunikativ kompetensiyalar ham sohaning ajralmas qismidir. Ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot bo‘lajak iqtisodchilarni tayyorlash jarayonida kasbiy-kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish zaruriyati, metodologiyasi va ahamiyatining muhokamasiga bag‘ishlanadi.

***Kalit so‘zlar:** o‘qituvchi, muloqot qobiliyatlari, kasbiy kompetensiyalar, iqtisodchi, integratsiyalashgan ta’lim, kommunikativ madaniyat, metod.*

INTRODUCTION

In the system of higher education in Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms continue to be carried out, related to the transition to a two-level training of education according to new standards. In this regard, the problems of improving the training of teachers of vocational training are very relevant, new educational technologies are being developed based on the integration of education, science and innovation, and a single intellectual, economic and cultural space is being formed [2].

Changing social and economic conditions in the country also require the preparation of an economically literate and enterprising master of economics, who knows how to rationally use the potential of his knowledge.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The implementation of the model for the formation of professional competencies of a specialist in economics is carried out at different types and forms

of conduct, goals and expected results of classroom activities: lectures, practical and laboratory classes. At lectures, the teacher sets out the general concept of the course, introduces students to the methodology for studying it, the requirements for the test / exam, etc. At seminars or practical classes in a dialogue mode, there is a more in-depth comprehension of the individual, most significant topics of the course; in laboratory classes, the necessary skills and abilities are worked out according to the course, in our case, this is how to conduct socio-economic surveys, make generalizations, mathematical processing of the data obtained, etc. The prerequisites for the technology of formation of professional competencies of the future economist in the process of studying the economic discipline are being created. The survey we conducted at the beginning of the course showed that most of the students' competencies were not formed even at the very initial stage, while we relied on the concepts of competence-based learning, the contextual approach, on the existing and tested pedagogical technologies (first of all, developmental learning technologies by L.V. Zankov, V.V. Davydov, I.S. Yakimanskaya, programmed learning by V.P. Bespalko, B.F.

Of course, we have not forgotten the general principles of education: scientific character, systematic approach, connection between theory and practice, continuity, etc. Creative competence - one of the key ones in the professional training of an economist - is defined as the ability to be creative. "A culturally oriented approach to education," says V.P. Salnikova, "is becoming more and more popular not only among the humanities, but also among economists [2]".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this article, we will try to consider only some of the main professional competencies of a future economist. The system of professional competencies is determined by us based on the research of I.V. Ovchinnikova (tab. 1).

Table 1.

System of professional competencies [1]

Competency Name	Definition	Compound
1	2	3
Communicative	The ability of a specialist to business constructive communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the ability to competently express one's point of view orally and in writing; -the ability to participate in discussions, to defend one's point of view; -knowledge of foreign languages; -the ability to present scientific and research materials; -knowledge of the basics of business communication; -willingness to work with general and special purpose software
Moral and social	Determines the responsibility of a specialist to society for his developments, projects, designs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledge about the rights and obligations of a specialist in the field of professional self-determination; - ability to analyze the situation in society; - ability to act in accordance with personal and social benefit; -respect for any individuality; - taking into account the requirements of safety and labor protection
Organizational	Ability to demonstrate organizational skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - team work skills; the ability to show oneself as a manager and executor of projects; -demonstrate independent work skills; - have practical skills in the organization of research and production work (in accordance with the profile); -ability to plan and organize relevant activities
Creative	Creativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - readiness for creative understanding and application of knowledge and skills in professional activities; - the ability to create and maintain a creative atmosphere in the team; - display of intuition, flexibility and originality of thinking

Gnostic	The ability to find, use, broadcast, apply theoretical and practical knowledge in practice and in various practical areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - have basic ideas about the diversity of objects of professional activity; -use knowledge in a specific area; - the ability to acquire new knowledge using modern information technologies; - ability to solve production and research problems; -to know various methods and forms of cognition and activity; - the ability to scientifically analyze the problems and processes of the professional field
Design	The totality of knowledge in a certain area, knowledge in the structure of project activities, the ability to apply this knowledge and skills in a specific activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the ability to develop sketches of parts, technical and working designs of structures, products of varying complexity; - ability to draw up instructions for the operation of structures and other technical literature; - ability to coordinate projects with other departments; -participation in the implementation of developed projects, testing, technical support
Research	Participation in works related to the search for new solutions to problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collection, processing, analysis, systematization of scientific and technical information on the topic; - study of special literature; -participation in scientific research, testing of prototypes of products; -analysis, processing of research results; -creation of test and control tools
Reflective	The ability of a specialist to evaluate his work, find himself in the chosen profession, the ability to self-regulate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -readiness to realize their activities; - the ability to see cause-and-effect relationships between tasks, goals, methods of implementation and performance results; - Ability to supervise and correct work at all stages.

All of these professional competencies are formed in the process of training a future specialist at a university, and we should talk about an integrated approach to training. Analyzing the state educational standard in the specialty, we see that among the special disciplines "State regulation of the economy" occupies a relatively small place: 36 hours, one semester, but, nevertheless, the knowledge, the content component of this discipline is used in many other disciplines, which, in turn, integrate their content components into this discipline. This is an organic and natural process in vocational training.

The professional competence of an economist as a whole has an integral characteristic, including: research, design, economic, analytical, organizational, managerial and pedagogical components, which ensure the quality of the performance of the relevant types of professional activities [10].

All types of professional activity are carried out primarily through communication, implemented at the verbal and non-verbal levels. In this regard, it is necessary to note the importance of communicative competence, which can be considered both as a component and as a condition and means of forming the professional competence of an economist.

I.A. Zimnyaya [4] in her work "Key competencies as a result-oriented basis of a competency-based approach in education" defines three groups of key competencies, highlighting as the central competence in the interaction of a person with other people. As a substantive aspect of this competence, I.A. Winter examines the competence of social interaction and competence in communication.

Thus, the communicative competence of an individual can be considered as a kind of "key" to the process of forming the professional competence of an economist, a means of forming the structural components of human capital as a whole.

In the educational process of higher education, the communicative competence of the teacher acquires special significance, since pedagogical communication is not only a means of scientific and pedagogical communication, but also a source of

development of the student's personality, a condition for the formation of his communicative and professional competence. Advanced pedagogical practice has brought the educational process to the level of "subject-subject" relations, considering it as a process of interaction, as a source of personal growth for both sides of the process.

Based on the analysis of scientific, pedagogical and psychological research, we have found that the process of forming the communicative competence of the student is directly dependent on the communicative competence of the teacher.

The communicative competence of a university teacher can be considered as "a system of internal resources necessary to build effective communication in a certain range of pedagogical situations of personal interaction in systems "teacher - student" and "teacher - teacher" [5, 6]. It presupposes the presence of knowledge, skills, abilities necessary for understanding others and building their own speech behavior programs that are adequate to the goals and situations of pedagogical communication.

Studies show that students, building a theoretical model of the "ideal teacher", following the criterion of competence within the discipline taught, put forward such criteria as goodwill in communication, respect for the student's personality, understanding, i.e. communication skills. The communicative abilities of a teacher, identified in the structure of pedagogical activity, along with gnostic, design and organizational ones, are considered by Z. F. Esareva as a combination of the following components:

- 1) the ability to establish communication in the systems "teacher - student" and "teacher - teacher";
- 2) the effectiveness of communication in these systems in terms of solving pedagogical problems.

The communicative abilities of a teacher have a pronounced intrinsic value, since they not only determine the quality of the process of transferring knowledge to students, but also influence the motivation of the further learning process within any

discipline being studied, thereby determining the quality of the process of forming professional competence in general.

Considering the formation of communicative competence and communicative culture in the process of preparing both bachelors and masters and graduate students, it should be noted that in practice there are two main contradictions that seriously complicate the possibilities of implementing this process. On the one hand, modern economic and political conditions for the development of society have determined the priority of business communication as the most massive in the field of social communication, implemented through speech activity. On the other hand, in the current situation in the field of higher education, there is a decrease in the level of communicative culture necessary for optimal self-realization of the individual in the process of business communication.

This contradiction is especially evident in the process of education in economic and technical universities. Communicative competence is a prerequisite for successful business communication in any area of interaction between the "person - person" system.

Studies show that in pedagogical practice, the communicative culture, the communicative competence of economists are far from the desired criteria of formation. In situations of pedagogical communication, students often switch to low-level speech stereotypes that are far from the concept of "communicative culture". An analysis of the reasons showed that several components can be distinguished in this problem, which are a complex combination of both speech and psychological and pedagogical aspects.

CONCLUSION

The future economist, who is aware of the determinism of his own career (and well-being in general) by the presence of a communicative culture and communicative competence, builds a qualitatively different motivation for learning in

studies. This has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the learning process and on the process of forming the professional competence of the future economist, including his intellectual capital as a whole.

REFERENCES

1. Ovchinnikova I.V. Formation of professional competence of aerospace specialists in the process of studying natural science disciplines: Abstract of the thesis. diss. cand. ped. Sciences. - Samara: 2019. - p. 11 - 12.
2. Salnikova V.P. Culturological grounds for the modernization of domestic education. - Samara: 2018. - P. 7.
3. Bodaleva A.A. Psychological communication. M.; Voronezh: Publishing House "Institute of Practical Psychology"; NPO "Modek", 2016. 256p.
4. Zimnyaya I. A. Key competencies as an effective-target basis of the competency-based approach in education. Author's version. M.: Research Center for Quality Problems in Training Specialists, 2014. 40 p.
5. Kozlova A. Professional deformations of the teacher's personality // Higher education in Russia. 2007. No. 3. P.141-143.
6. Ovsyannikova O.A. Psychological and pedagogical aspects of the problem of the formation of the communicative competence of a university teacher // Humanitarian sciences at the beginning of the third millennium: monograph / ed. A.V. Repnikov. St. Petersburg: Info-da, 2017. p.73-90.
7. Ovsyannikova O.A., Suganova M.I., Pravdyuk V.N. The role of the category "human capital" in the formation of professional competence of future masters in economics. // News of TulGU. Pedagogy. Issue 1. Tula: Publishing House of TulGU, 2014. p. 145-152.
8. Pravdyuk V.N., Ovsyannikova O.A. Psychological and pedagogical competence of the teacher as a condition for the success of the pedagogical process in

the university // Uchenye zapiski Oryol State University. Series "Humanities and social sciences". 2012. No. 2. p. 303-309.

9. Usanova O.G. Formation of the teacher's communicative competence in the process of pedagogical communication // Russian speech in a modern university: materials of the Second Intern. scientific-practical. internet conferences. Orel: Orel GTU, 2016. p.129-133.

10. Рашидов, Д. (2022). TRANSPORT KORXONALARI UCHUN NOGIRONLAR TOMONIDAN ISHLAB CHIQRILAYOGAN MAXSUS KIYIMLAR VA BOSHQA MAHSULOTLAR XARIDINI KO 'PAYTIRISH ORQALI NOGIRONLAR MEHNATINI RAG'BATLANTIRISH. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

11. Sharipov F.V. Professional competence of a university teacher // Higher education today. 2010. №1. pp. 72–77.